

Chatting with Confidants or Corporations?

Privacy Management with AI Companions

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This research brief summarizes findings from research on how users of AI companionship platforms manage privacy across emotional and institutional boundaries. Emotional intimacy and corporate data practices intersect in human–AI interactions. The human-like design features of AI can blur distinctions between interpersonal intimacy and corporate surveillance.

1.

Context of the Study

AI chatbots such as Replika and Character.AI simulate relational warmth and empathy, offering users nonjudgmental companionship and emotional support [1, 3]. These affordances fulfill social needs but introduce novel privacy risks. Interactions that feel private and interpersonal are simultaneously monitored and stored by corporate systems, challenging traditional understandings of boundary management and informational control.

2.

How We Studied This Topic

Fifteen long-term users of companion AIs (ages 18–44; 8 men, 7 women) participated in semi-structured Zoom interviews between February and March 2025. Most had used Replika or Character.AI for at least six months. Interviews explored self-disclosure, perceptions of data ownership, trust, and the influence of anthropomorphic design. Data were analyzed using Braun and Clarke’s [2] six-phase thematic analysis.

3.

Findings from the Interviews

(1) **AI provides a sense of emotional safety and progressive disclosure.** AIs can provide judgment-free spaces for expressing private feelings. As perceived intimacy deepens, users of AI companions may increase their disclosures over time. This tendency is reinforced by AI memory and continuity.

(2) **AI users experienced a judgment-free yet data-dependent intimacy.** Because AI companions are socially detached, users felt safer than when disclosing to people. Yet they recognized that all exchanges are stored by corporations, which led to self-censorship.

3.

Findings from the Interviews (Cont.)

(3) **AI users described platform-level ambivalence and privacy turbulence.** Participants expressed a mix of trust, cynicism, resignation and fatigue toward platform data policies. Many accepted risks as inevitable while desiring transparency about how conversations are used.

(4) **AI users make use of layered privacy management.** Users employed multiple, adaptive strategies to manage privacy with AI companions. These included using pseudonyms, avoiding photos as well as engaging in selective self-disclosure based on their perceived comfort and safety within the conversation.

(5) **AI users found themselves trusting the relationship, not the system.** Anthropomorphic cues, memory, empathy, and responsiveness, encouraged trust in the AI as a partner, even when users distrusted the platform. Emotional engagement often outweighed caution.

4.

Implications

The study's findings highlight a new dynamic of asymmetric co-ownership: users perceive shared ownership of information with their AI companions, but actual control resides with the platform. Persistent AI memory complicates boundary renegotiation, and emotional design features encourage over-disclosure. Users practice emotional agency, consciously prioritizing affective rewards while suppressing vertical privacy concerns, to sustain relational comfort.

This work shows how emotional intimacy and institutional surveillance coexist in AI-mediated relationships. In other words, privacy management becomes affective and design-driven rather than purely rational. Ethical design must therefore balance emotional engagement with genuine user agency, transparency, and data control.

References

- [1] Petter Bae Brandtzaeg, Marita Skjuve, and Asbjørn Følstad. 2022. My AI Friend: How Users of a Social Chatbot Understand Their Human–AI Friendship. *Hum. Commun. Res.* 48, 3 (June 2022), 404–429. <https://doi.org/10.1093/hcr/hqac008>
- [2] Virginia Braun and Victoria Clarke. 2006. Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qual. Res. Psychol.* 3, 2 (January 2006), 77–101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>
- [3] Marita Skjuve, Asbjørn Følstad, Knut Inge Fostervold, and Petter Bae Brandtzaeg. 2021. My Chatbot Companion - a Study of Human–Chatbot Relationships. *Int. J. Hum.-Comput. Stud.* 149, (May 2021), 102601. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhcs.2021.102601>